

SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS OF A MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF THE ADOPTIVE CELLULAR THERAPY AND CYTOKINE INJECTIONS FOR CANCER MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

Sensitivity analysis of a mathematical model of immunotherapy of adoptive cellular therapy with cytokine IL-2 injections for tumor treatment is studied. Model consists of three nonlinear ordinary differential equations with population of tumor cells, effector cells or activated immune cell and concentration of cytokine IL-2 drug are the three variables along with fourteen parameters. For sensitivity analysis ARS algorithm of Painleve property analysis for system of nonlinear ordinary differential equations is used and found the mathematical model is stable for all values of parameters. Hence this study suggests boosting of body's immune system by using cytokines like IL-2 is better than other therapies for tumor managements.

Keywords: Immunotherapy, tumor, chemotherapy, biomarkers, cytokines, cytotoxic T lymphocytes, dendritic cells, protine, effector cells, progenitors, opsonin, ligand, resonances, Painleve.

1. Introduction

Immunotherapy or Biological Therapy or Biotherapy is proposed in 2009 as a future medicine by Duc Hing Le [01], [2], [3], [4]. Immunotherapy treatment for cancer means boosting of the body's own immune system to identify and fight cancer by enhancing or restoring immune responses in order to destroy malignant cancer cells at the same time not attacking the healthy cells [2], [3], [4], [5], [6], [7]. Immunotherapy generally recommends for certain types of cancer such as advanced lung cancer, kidney cancer or the cancer has specific biomarkers like high PD-L1 expression or happened many genetic changes. Immunotherapy is also recommended for diseases like autoimmune disorders, allergies, and some infectious diseases. Immunotherapy is generally used in advanced stages of cancer when other therapies like chemotherapy, radiotherapy etc fails to control the cancer

growth. Generally this failure happened [2], [3],[5],[8], when cancer cells sometimes hide from body's immune system by mimicking like normal healthy cells or immune cells fail to identify cancer cells as foreign bodies when they are much similar to normal cells or might not be strong enough to destroy the cancer cells . Sometimes cancer cells produce signals that enable them hide from immune system. Such cases immunotherapy boosting body's own immune system and recognize cancer cells or strengthening to detect cancer cells and kill them. In chemotherapy drugs directly killing the cancer cells along with healthy cells whereas, immunotherapy drugs never directly killing the cancer cells but helping body's own immune system to kill or control the progression of cancer cells [2],[3],[6],[7].

Generally cancer begins with rapid mutation or protein changes in the genes called biomarkers that are different in different patients even for same type of cancer [1],[2],[3],[6],[7]. Immunotherapy targets biomarkers of cancer. Some of the gene or protein changes that immunotherapy's drug can be identified are Programmed cell death-1 protein (PD-1), Programmed death-ligand protein (PD-L1), Cytotoxic T lymphocytes –associated protein -4 (CTLA-4) , microsatellite instability (MSI), Cluster of differentiations -19 (CD-19), Cluster of differentiation -20 (CD-20) ,B cell maturation antigen (BCM), G protein-coupled receptor family C group 5 member D (GPRC5D), cluster of differentiation 38 protein (CD38) etc.

There are many types of immune cells [2] [3],[5],[6],[7] , macrophages, helper T, regulator T, memory T , dendritic , helper B, effector B and memory B ,all these cells derived from myloid progenitors and lymphoid progenitors. In which dendritic cells and macrophages are antigen presenting cells (APC) are main immune boosters and they able to identify the invader or cancer cells without making any harm to healthy cells. Immune cells or lymphocytes in the blood stream moving to the site of the tumor , that are called tumor-infiltrating lymphocytes (TILs).There are two types of immune response to invader cells or cancer cells, innate Immune response or non-specific immune response and adoptive immune response or specific immune response. In innate immune response or non-specific immune response when invader cell or cancer cell is detected by the immune system then either counter acts using its nonspecific fighters like phagocytotoxic leukocytes and killer cells like monocytes ,neutrophils , mast cells, and macrophages or using pathogen specific fighters(not specific to a particular pathogen) like B and T cells. In Adoptive Immune response the type of pathogen is first identified according to the antigen present on them then that antigen specific immune cells like helper , effector and memory cells are activated and using signaling molecules effector cells killing that specific pathogen.

There are two opposite processes for regulating the immune system like competition of a predator–prey interactive system of two species [2], [3],[5],[6],[7],[8],[9] [10],[11]. These are co-stimulatory and co-inhibitory responses of immune systems. Co-stimulatory or activatory or immunogenic pathways positively reciprocate whenever an immune response arises. For successful completion of co-stimulatory pathways of immune response T cell activation process needs two signals. One antigen-specific signal via major histocompatibility complex (MHC) molecules and second, co-stimulatory signals between T cell receptor and its ligand CD80 on antigen presenting cells (APCs) [12]. This process is able to boost the immune response. Whereas, co-inhibitory pathways reduce or block immune response by binding of PD-1 receptor with its ligand PD-L1. [13]. So the successful controlling of the co-inhibitory pathways able to reduce the pathogen or cancer cells load is one method of cancer management. The co-inhibitory pathways of blocking of immune response is for body's way of 'controlling autoimmunity.

Dendritic, macrophages and B cells are antigen presenting cells (APC) able to identify pathogens and direct respective immune cells to kill them [2], [3],[6],[7],[8], [14],[15],[16]. Opsonization is another method of destroying pathogens by marking them using opsonin molecules like immunoglobulin G-*IgG* that tags the pathogen so helps macrophages or dendritic cells engulf the pathogen. So boosting of production of opsonin molecules is one possible procedure to reduce the pathogen load or cancer cells population.

Adoptive cell transfer (ACT) or Adoptive transfer of activated T cells is a method of boosting immunity, in which T cells are cultured and administered to the patient. For this IL-2 activated killer cells are also used. [17]. For vaccination treatment the therapeutic drugs either developed from tumor of the patient or cultured [44]. Vaccination treatment through Dendritic cells for boosting the immune response for regression of tumor also a method of cancer management. Even then tumor cells are able to produce PDL-1 to bind the proliferation of T cells and that leads to apoptosis of T cells, that helps fast multiplication of cancer cells. Such case immunotherapy helps the killer cell to identify those escaped cancer cells and kill them.

In this study, the mathematical model of Kirschner-Panetta [18]- [24] is used, that is widely discussed in many clinical studies in which interactions among tumor cells, effector cells, and IL-2 cytokine concentration are studied. All activated cells that are capable to kill tumor cells are considered as effector cells. IL-2 cytokines connecting the expression of co-inhibiting receptors such as PD-1 which regulates the proliferation and differentiation of

immune cells like T and B cells . It is assumed that the volume of IL-2 directly proportional to proliferation of Immune cells [19] . There are three nonlinear ordinary differential equations as,

$$\frac{dH}{dt} = b_1T - b_9H + b_3u_1(t) + \frac{\rho_1HC}{(b_4+T)}, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dT}{dt} = b_5T(-bT) - \frac{c_1HT}{(b_6+T)}, \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = b_7u_2(t) + \frac{\rho_2HT}{(b_9+T)} - d_U C, \quad (3)$$

where dependent variable $H(t)$ is the volume of active mature cytokine Tcells or effector cells , $T(t)$ is the tumor cell volume and $C(t)$ is the volume of cytotoxic concentration with cytokine IL-2

Parameters are $u(t)$ is the control input corresponding to any type of ACT such as the lymphokine-activated killer (LAK) cell therapy or tumor-infiltrating lymphocyte (TIL) therapy, $u_2(t)$ is the second input that accounts for administration of IL-2 injection as an immune boosting adjuvant. b_1 is the parameter modeling antigenicity of the tumor which represents the extent to which tumor cells express their antigens. b_9 is the death rate of effector cells , b_3 is the treatment factor tht enhance the effector cell population, ρ_1 and ρ_2 are the immune response rates , b_4 , b_6 and b_9 are half saturation constants , b_5 is the growth rate , b is the inverse carrying capacity, c_1 is the competition rate , b_7 is the IL-2 concentration and d_U is the depletion rate cytokine.

Cytokines are signal proteins play important role in the controlling of viral load. There are three types of important cytokines , Chemokines, Interferons , and interleukines . Interferons (γ IFN₁) having antiviral and antitumor properties. Interleukines cytokines produced by T cells , macrophages, monocytes that boost the growth and differentiate of T and B cells whenever body's defence mechanism identifies the invader cell tumor presence that activate the proliferation of effector cells .In b_1A the term b_1 is a parameter stands for antigenicity of the tumor denotes the extent to which tumor express their antigens .the term $d_1H(T)$ denotes the apoptosis of the effector cells ,in which d_1 denotes the death rate of effector cells $H(t)$. The parameters b_3 and b_7 of the terms b_3u_1 and b_7u_2 respectively denote the effect of administration of external adjuvant of cytokine drugs to felicitate immunotherapy. Where b_3 parameter denotes the contribution of boosting of effector cells

population and b_7 denotes contribution of boosting of concentration of cytokine IL-2 [20]. Parameter b_5 denotes the growth rate of tumor cells volume and so increase in volume of tumor due to carrying capacity is $b_5 T$ and the restriction of growth rate of volume of tumor cells T due to limitation of carrying capacity is $b b_5 T^2$, where b is the inverse carrying capacity. Parameter c_1 denotes competition rate between H and T population and parameter b_6 is the half saturation constant. Term $d_U C(t)$ is the depletion or decrease rate of IL-2 concentration [23], [24].

In this study, the sensitivity analysis of above mathematical model of adoptive cellular therapy and cytokine drug IL-2 administration for cancer management is studied by using ARS algorithm for Painleve property analysis (PPA) for nonlinear ordinary differential equations.

2. Stability analysis by Painleve property analysis (PPA) of nonlinear ordinary differential equations, ars algorithm.

In the study of nonlinear dynamical systems, chaos has measured by an extreme sensitivity of the solutions to the control parameter associated with the initial conditions. Equations whose solutions are free from any chaotic irregular behaviour are called 'completely integrable', that are characterized by regular or predictable behaviour for all values of initial conditions and for all time. Whereas, in 'non-integrable' systems, their regions in the phase space of their dependent variables the motion is irregular and chaotic. This type of study initiated by Sonya Kowaleveskaya [25] in the context of rotating bodies, is the first attempt in dynamical systems associated with singularities.

There are two types singularities, first one called fixed singularity in which their location of singularity determined by the equation itself, second type is the movable singularity where its locations depends on the initial conditions. Fixed singularity type is absent in linear equations, but in nonlinear ordinary differential equations (ODEs) both types of singularities are possible.

Painleve' found three types of second order nonlinear ODEs with only movable singularities are poles [26]. Then Gambier added three more such types in 1916 and concluded no their cases arising in second order nonlinear ordinary differential equations [25], this property is called Painleve' Property (PP). An algorithm developed by Ablowitz, Ramani and Segur called ARS algorithm [27], [28] for system of nonlinear ordinary first order

differential equations that admits singularities as movable branch points, either algebraic or logarithmic. That ARS algorithm is using in this study for PP analysis of (1) - (3).

Let us consider a system of ordinary differential equations (ODEs) of the form

$$\frac{du^i}{dt} = F_i(u^1, u^2, \dots, u^n), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n. \quad (4)$$

For dominant behaviour of the solutions in the neighbourhood of a movable singularity of the form

$$u^i = \alpha_i \tau^{\rho_i}, \quad \text{where } \tau = (t_0 - t), \quad (5)$$

are to be searched. For that three steps for the ARS algorithm;

Step 01

Substitute equation (5) in (4) and find all possible values ρ_i , for which two or more leading ordered terms in each equation balance each other, and the rest can be ignored for each such choice of the ρ_i . Also find all possible values of α_i .

Step 02

Keep only the leading ordered balancing terms of step 01 and ignore rest and substitute

$$u^i = \alpha_i \tau^{\rho_i} (1 + \gamma_i \tau^r) \quad (6)$$

All product terms of γ_i are to be omitted, then system reduced to

$$Q(r) \cdot \gamma = 0, \quad \text{where } \gamma = (\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \dots, \gamma_n). \quad (7)$$

Where $Q(r)$ is a $(n \times n)$ matrix in which r entering only in its diagonal elements, almost linearly. Find the roots of the determinant of

$$\text{Det } Q(r) = 0, \quad (8)$$

These values of r are called resonances. Resonance determines the number of arbitrary constants exist in the system of ODEs (4). Resonance $r = -1$ is related to the location of the one free constant, namely t_0 the point of the singularity and that always appear in the roots of (5).

The resonance $r = 0$ corresponds to the coefficient of one of the the leading ordered terms being arbitrary. Any resonance with real valued and $r > 0$ but not an integer indicates at $t = t_0$ is a movable singularity.

We have to evaluate all possible distinct $(n - 1)$ nonnegative and real valued integer resonances. Less than $(n - 1)$ nonnegative and real valued distinct integer resonances implies system has no PP property. The given system of ODEs having no PP when any of the ρ_j of τ^{ρ_j} is positive value or any of the resonances is not integer or repeated.

3. Sensitivity analysis of the mathematical model by PP analysis

Only possible balancing pairs of dominated terms of the above mathematical model (1)-(3) are

$$b_4 \frac{dH}{dt} = b_1 TC, \tag{9}$$

$$b_9 \frac{dT}{dt} = -c_1 HT, \tag{10}$$

$$b_9 \frac{dC}{dt} = \rho_2 HT. \tag{11}$$

Substitute,

$$H = \alpha \tau^p, T = \beta \tau^q, \text{ and } C = \lambda \tau^s \tag{12}$$

In above equations (1)-(3) and evaluate values of $p, q, s, \alpha, \beta, \text{ and } \lambda$, yield,

$$p = q = s = -1, \tag{13}$$

$$\alpha = \frac{b_6}{c_1}, \beta^2 = \frac{b_9 b_4}{b_1 \rho_2}, \text{ and } \lambda = -\frac{b_4 b_6}{b_1 \rho_2}. \tag{14}$$

For finding resonance substitute

$$H = \alpha \tau^p (1 + \gamma \tau^r), T = \beta \tau^q (1 + \delta \tau^r) \text{ and } C = \lambda \tau^s (1 + \eta \tau^r), \tag{15}$$

In (9)-(11) and evaluate equations for γ, δ, η in terms of resonance r , that yield

$$(r - 1)\gamma + \delta + \eta = 0, r\delta + \gamma = 0 \text{ and } (r - 1)\eta + \gamma + \delta = 0. \tag{8}$$

Corresponds to above three linear equations (8) values of the resonance r can be obtained from the determinant,

$$\begin{vmatrix} (r-1) & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & r & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & (r-1) \end{vmatrix} = 0 . \quad (9)$$

Gives the values of resonances as

$$r = -1, +1, +2 , \quad (10)$$

all values of resonances r are distinct integers and so satisfied ARS algorithm of PPA [27],[28]. This means dynamical system corresponds equations (1)-(3) is stable for all values of parameters .

4. Conclusion

Cancer is a large class of diseases with general characteristics are repeated ,rapid and uncontrolled division cells cycle and spreading to other parts of the body. The progression and metastasis of tumor depends on the carrying capacity of the tumor microenvironment. Tumor in an organism is a group of surviving abnormal or mutated cells that can outsmart the body's inherent tumor suppressing mechanism like tumor suppressor genes ,immune response.

When an immune cell encounter tumor cell leads to annihilation ,inhibition or survival of the anomalous cell, that controlled by many cytokine signal pathways. Tumor-immune interaction is protein-protein interaction and is a complex process among many types of cells. The immune system consists of different types of cells like, natural killer cells, macrophages ,cytotoxic T cells, helper cells, memory cells, dendritic cells ,etc. Tumor-immune interaction is of two types ,innate immune action and adoptive immune action so as to kill anomalous invader pathogens at the same time protect host's healthy normal cells [3], [30].

Antigens are proteins that trigger immune action and promote production of specific antibodies. .Immune cells like dendritic cells and macrophages having receptors to identify the antigen of the pathogens and cancer cells .Cytokines are cell signaling proteins promote proliferation, mutation , suppression and activation of various cell populations like T cells ,macrophages [30]. Cytokine like TGF- β , IL-23 having both tumor inhibition, invasion and metastasis along with suppression of tumor [3],[31]. Immune system capable to annihilates most of the cancer cells still some of the cancer cells may escape and rapidly proliferate such case external suitable adjuvant like cytokines are to be administered in order to boost

immune system to identify the escaped cancer cells and facilitate tumor lysis [3] at the same time do no hindrance to the host healthy cells. The purpose of immunotherapy is boosting of immune system or assists the immune system in the process of identification and killing of cancer cells and protect healthy cells. So the dynamics of tumor-immune interaction consists of various cells like naïve or matured immune cells such as helper T cells, memory T cells, T regulator cells, cytotoxic T cells, dendritic cells, and their reaction with anti-tumor cytokines like IL-2, pro-tumor cytokine like TGF- β , IL-10, IL-23 [18],[29]. For that various strategies like adoptive cellular therapy and cytokine injections, dendritic vaccination, immune checkpoint inhibition, administration of immune-stimulatory cytokines like IL-2 for activating natural killer cells. Oncolytic viruses are using to the immunogenicity of tumor cell, they are genetically modified viruses for targeting tumor cell lysis, etc using according to the types, location, age and health of the patient.

In the present study the sensitivity analysis of the nonlinear dynamics of the mathematical model of adoptive cellular therapy and the effect of cytokine IL-2 injections is studied by using PPA method for nonlinear dynamical systems modeled by system of nonlinear ordinary differential equations. According to the final results of the mathematical analysis the resonances are all integers independent of any parameters. Hence dynamics of the system is very well stable for all values of parameters of the model [27],[28]. Even then model is developed for cytokine IL-2 alone, in addition IL-7, IL-15, IL-21 are also suitable for boosting immune system [33],[34]. These drugs are generally prepared from the tumor of the patient for better adoptability purpose.

Immunotherapy administration given daily, weekly, monthly often at regular intervals called cycles. A cycle means one or more followed by a break. Number of cycles depends on stage of tumor, type, health age of the patient. Administrations are intravenous or orally or topical. Possible side effects are, skin changes such as rash, fatigue, nausea vomiting or diarrhea, endocrine changes like thyroid changes, flu like symptoms, cytokine release syndrome, neurologic toxicity, and colitis. Even then these side effects are not so severe compared to other therapies like chemotherapy, radiation therapy. Recently It is shown that a mathematical model of chemotherapy having unstable dynamics and the respective control parameters are all depend on boosting of immune cells [35].

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